

Towards a Workload Mapping Model for Tuning Backing Services in Cloud Systems

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Abstract. With the increasing advent of applications and services adopting cloud-based technologies, generic automated tuning techniques of database services are gaining much attraction. This work identifies and proposes to overcome the potential challenges associated with deploying a tuning service as part of Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) offerings for tuning of backing services. Offering an effective database tuning service requires such tuners whose architecture can support tuning multiple databases and numerous database versions deployed on various types of underlying hardware configurations with varying VM plans. Tuners that offer such capabilities usually attempt to leverage experiences gathered previously. By taking advantage of relevant past experiences, tuners classify the current workload to the most pertinent workload seen recently. In this work, a five-layered, fully connected neural network with ReLU activation function is being employed as the classification model to classify data points into relevant workload classes. The categorical cross-entropy function is employed as the loss function and optimized using Adam optimizer. The work handles the challenges related to the cold-start problem, issues in mapping, and cascading errors. The proposed solution can overcome these issues in a large-scale production environment. The results show that the model has 93.3% accuracy in 93.8% F1-score as compared to the previous model like Ottertune.

Keywords: Knobs · Central Tuner · ANN · Softmax probability · Metric Collector.

1 Introduction

With the rising popularity of micro-services in Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) and Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) architectures in recent years, backing services have become an integral part of a cloud. These architectures become quintessential for consumption by microservices to enable functionalities like data stores and messaging systems [1, 2]. Examples of such backing services can be datastores like MySQL, PostgreSQL, Redis, CouchDB, etc., and messaging services like RabbitMQ, Apache Kafka, etc. Platform customers do not have access to tune the configuration knobs for such underlying backing service. The sheer magnitude of the backing service deployments makes it impossible for the service

providers to hire a DBA/administrator for real-time tuning of databases. A diverse range of backing service offerings from a platform also adds another layer of complexity [3].

To deal with such situations, it is evident that a highly robust and scalable approach for auto-tuning backing services is required. One such solution is Ottertune [4], which can tune multiple backing services irrespective of different versions and vendors. Ottertune Style Tuners (OST) has been introduced as a generic term used throughout the work to refer to all such tuners employing an architecture similar to Ottertune. OST recommendation engines always have a cost associated with each recommendation request executed for production systems. For service providers, the cost of provisioning a tuner deployment becomes challenging, as a single OST tuner deployment can provide tuning service to a limited number of service-instance. Also, the value of the recommendation becomes important since a customer is charged for each generated recommendation. Thus, an ideal goal is to maximize the number of deployments associated with a single tuning service deployment. These criteria must be maintained while ensuring that the accuracy of the recommendation is not compromised and the performance of the database instances subscribing to the service stays optimal. These tuning-service architectures employ machine learning algorithms for two essential operations: classification and recommendation. As per the model followed by OST recommendation engines and other proprietary tuners, the following issues are observed in the case of real-time production-ready deployment.

- **Cold-start problem:** The accuracy of mapping a workload to the most similar workloads (optimal mapping) increases only with the increasing size of the source workload. This is evident from the fact that the predicted metrics are computed where the length of predicted metrics equals the total knobs attempted in the source workload. The source workload is the workload set being executed on the database instance that is requested for tuning. If the size of the source workload is less (the database has recently been registered to the tuning service), it has observed lesser data points, then the OST recommendation engines suffer higher error percentages in mapping to the target workload. Due to wrong mappings, the obtained recommendations often lead to degradation in transactions per second (tps) on production systems. One such case is when a read-heavy/oriented workload gets mapped to a write heavy/oriented workload, and the obtained recommendations are always inclined to favour write optimal configurations and, in the end, even degrading.
- **Issues of deep mapping:** OST recommendation engine maps an entire source workload to a new target workload which requires a huge number of data points to be already present in the database instance. The prerequisite is that, the target workloads should have huge observational data points for higher accuracy in mapping. Thus, the workloads seen in the past need to observe all sorts of variations in knobs and metrics for a smoother implemen-

tation. This technique becomes not only tedious but also non-deterministic since such training cannot always be guaranteed.

- **Issues of self mapping:** Another major flaw in the OST recommendation engine is that the engine considers the source workload to be one of the potential candidates for the target workload. Since the evaluation of the score depends on the predicted metrics set and its Euclidean distance to the input metric set. There are chances that the score could have come minimum for the target workload, which is the same as the source workload. Such a mapping is completely erroneous and leads to further degradation in the performance of the tuning service for the database instance.
- **Cascading errors:** The impact of the limitations discussed above has a drastic cascading effect. Let us visualize this with an example. Suppose the OST recommendation engine performs an erroneous mapping because of the above limitations and maps the source data point to a wrong target workload. This not only affects the current recommendation request but also corrupts the source workload.

Considering such challenges, in this work, a similar issue has been identified in a real-time deployment employing Ottertune’s approach, where the chances of missing SLAs became very high. OST uses previously gained experiences to generate a new recommendation. In [4], authors use Euclidean Distance to map the incoming workload (from any given production workload) to one of the most similar workloads observed in the past. However, as the optimal recommendation generation solely depends upon mapping to such a similar workload, low accuracy of mapping on production systems can even reduce the final throughput drastically. Built upon such challenges, the proposed work identifies such issues with the OST tuning approach deployed for large databases and proposes solutions for the same. The major contributions of this paper are as follows:

- The proposed method maximizes the capability of the tuner by gathering relevant and most recent experiences from the data aggregator.
- A Neural Network is employed as the classifier model to classify data points into relevant workload classes. The classifier used a five-layered, fully connected neural network with ReLU activation. The last layer is a Softmax layer for classification into workload classes.
- The model is trained on the historical set of data for the workloads using categorical cross entropy function as the loss function and optimized using Adam optimizer.
- Further, the work has been compared with Ottertune and measured the F1-score and accuracy.

2 Related Work

There exist multiple works which focus on tuning databases based on physical or logical design [5], index tuning [6], or partitioning schemes [7, 8]. Some works focus on tuning a subset of performance-impacting knobs [9]. There are also possible sets of tuners exist that are specific to certain commercial databases, such as DB2’s Performance Wizard Tool [10], Oracle’s Database Monitoring Tools [11], and Tuner for Microsoft SQL [12]. However, these tuners are limited by specific vendor dependencies and lack a generic approach for tuning certain knob parameters to achieve a specific objective. There are also some tuners that are based on feedback-driven techniques [13], [14] which tune certain knobs by executing benchmarks and then observing performance details. Later, the same performance details/ statistics are used to recommend changes in the database to make it perform better. Authors used an Ottertune-style knob tuner that leverages large-scale machine-learning techniques to furnish optimal recommendations for a database [15]. OST provide a common platform which can fetch metrics from multiple types of databases based on various VM plans as given by infrastructure providers like AWS, Alibaba Cloud, Azure, Google Cloud Platform, etc. They can use large-scale machine-learning techniques to provide knob recommendations. Keeping in mind the challenges faced by Platform-as-a-Service offerings, this architecture seems to be a scalable solution which can be used for tuning the backing service offerings. The Ottertune Style Tuners (OST) capture the experience gathered from different production databases and then leverages the experiences gained to give an optimal recommendation. Ottertune maps a current workload to one of the closest seen workloads and then uses the experiences (physical features) gained from the mapped workload to provide an optimal recommendation.

There are a couple of other works which use arrival-rate history [16] and query’s logical semantics [17] to perform similar clustering of workloads. However, there is a reasonable consensus that OST engines are the best fit for this use case, as these features help in better clustering without understanding the query meaning. Moreover, these features are more sensitive towards database physical design and hardware. However, in [4], authors use Euclidean distance to estimate the closest workload seen previously. Euclidean distance has certain drawbacks to use in the production environment. In this work, we highlight such challenges associated with the mapping of a workload and propose solutions for the same. In [18] author explained how the cold-start could be a large problem in the case of database systems as well as in the field of big data. Also, the authors explained how the cascading error could be detected in the back-propagation while training the model.

Keeping in mind the challenges faced by PaaS offerings, this work proposed an architecture that tunes the backing services. The proposed method captures the experience gathered from different production databases and then leverages the experiences gained to give an optimal recommendation.

3 System Design

3.1 Problem Formulation

At any given time instant t , let's assume D is the set of all database service instances subscribing to the tuning-service deployment provisioned as part of PaaS offerings. N denotes the total number of such instances, such that: $D = \{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_n, \dots, D_N\}$. The set of database service instances denoted by D bind to a single tuning-service deployment, and the tuning recommendations need to be served for all such instances in real-time from the single tuner deployment only. Consequently, the experience gained by the tuning service for tuning database instance, D_1 , is stored by the tuning service as workload, W_1 . Then, W^P can be defined as the set of all workloads, such that workload W_n^P stores experience obtained from database instance D_n . $W^P = \{W_1^P, W_2^P, \dots, W_N^P\}$. Furthermore, each workload stores this experience in the form of multiple points, each point is denoted by a duplet, $\{k_i, m_i\}_{W_n}$, where for each n^{th} workload, k denotes the knobs (physical settings configured), m denotes the metrics captured (statistics representing performance) for database D_n at time instant t . Further, consider that W^O denotes the set of workloads generated offline (non-production system) by executing various SQL workload benchmarks like TPCC, YCSB, Twitter, etc. These offline workloads often use multiple mixtures of a certain benchmark to showcase enough variations, e.g., $\{\text{Read}\%, \text{Write}\%\}$ mixture of TPCC has variations like $\{50, 50\}$, $\{60, 40\}$, $\{80, 20\}$, $\{20, 80\}$. Any such workload can be denoted as W_k^O , and the set of all such workloads of total size K can be represented by $W^O = \{W_1^O, W_2^O, \dots, W_k^O, \dots, W_K^O\}$. Let us assume W_n^{source} denotes the workload of a database making a recommendation request. Each time an underlying database service instance sends a request for tuning to the tuning service (at time instance t), the input parameters from the database instance to the tuner service are denoted as $\{k_i, m_i\}_{W_n^{source}}$. The tuning service, then, needs to map the received data-point $k_i, m_i_{W_n^{source}}$ to any given previously observed workload $W_{k \neq n}$. This mapping is essential because the data points present in the mapped workload, $W_{k \neq n}$, are used to train the Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) engine in order to provide a recommendation to the requesting database instance.

3.2 Mapping Workload

Here, the problem of mapping a source workload to an existing workload is formulated. The section helps in understanding how the mapping of a workload is tackled by an OST recommendation engine. Continuing from the previous section, if for a time instant t , a tuning request is triggered by a database service instance to the tuning service, and the tuning service receives a new data point, $\{k_i, m_i\}_{W_n^{source}}$. Now, the OST engine employs a ranking/purging methodology to determine top-ranked knobs (characterized by knob ids) and metrics (characterized by metric ids). The engine further filters the current data point, i.e. $\{k_i, m_i\}_{W_n^{source}}$ and keeps the dimensions of knobs and metrics as per the newly

obtained knob-ids and metric-ids. The OST engine then proceeds with the pre-processing tasks like binning, normalization, computing deciles, binning, etc. Now, leveraging the workloads experienced by the tuning agent denoted by W^P and the workloads that are generated offline denoted by W^O , the tuning engine has a total of $W^P \cup W^O$ workloads. For each workload in $(W^P \cup W^O)$, the algorithm trains a (Gaussian Process Regression) GPR and obtains a new predicted metrics set denoted by M^{pred} from the trained GPR for all knob set ($\forall k \in W_n^{source}$) attempted in workload W_n^{source} . Finally, as per the algorithm, the Euclidean distance is calculated and averaged for corresponding metrics, i.e., M^{pred} and $M^{original}$ where $M^{original}$ is the set of all actual metrics observed in workload W_n^{source} . The Euclidean distance is calculated for all predicted metrics and actual metrics. Similarly, for each workload, the Euclidean distance is calculated, and the workload with the least score wins.

3.3 Proposed Classification Approach

As discussed in the previous section, the Euclidean distance-based approach for workload mapping in the OST engine has drawbacks and can cause Service Level Agreement (SLA) violations for production scenarios. It requires a huge number of data points in W_n^{source} before the model converges to an optimum solution. The time of convergence increases with an increase in the number of data points as well. So, on the one hand, we require a large amount of data points before the model can accurately predict the workload class for incoming data points. Having a large number of data points leads to an increase in the time required to predict relevant classes for new test data points. To solve all these shortcomings, we have used a Neural Network as the classifier model to classify data points into relevant workload classes. This significantly reduces the test time required to optimally predict the workload class.

The used classifier is a five-layered, fully connected neural network with ReLU activation. The last layer is a Softmax layer for classification into workload classes (for example, in one of our test cases, into five workload classes). The structure of the ANN model has shown in Fig. 1. The model is trained on the historical set of data for the workloads using categorical cross entropy function as the loss function and optimized using Adam optimizer. We have used accuracy as the optimizing metric and time for one test run as the satisfying metric. The classifier is trained with a total of n workloads (at any time instance t), which create a total of n classes. Now with the proposed classification approach, any new point $\{k_i, m_i\}_{W_n^{source}}$, which comes from a W_n^{source} , gets classified to one of the classes using the trained model. As the classification approach classifies a point instead of classifying the whole source workload, this seems to minimize the highlighted mapping drawback. The dimensions of training data depend on the globally ranked knobs and metrics. This ranking is done by the background tasks such as factor analysis, clustering, and Lasso’s feature extraction algorithm.

Theoretically, there is also a high chance that with each trigger of a background task, the globally ranked knobs get changed, which changes the dimensions of the

data and ultimately leads to the retraining of the neural network. The retraining is triggered only when a change is encountered in the set of globally ranked metrics and knobs. However, in production environments, it is observed that this change is seen only when a new database service instance gets added up.

Fig. 1: Structure of ANN having softmax as activation function and CE as loss function

4 System Architecture

This section explains the architecture of the proposed Autonomous Database-as-a-Service model (ADBaaS) when deployed by a PaaS service provider. Fig. 2 represents ADBaaS in which the tuning service is modularized into various components. It can be noted that the tuning service is completely de-coupled from the platform architecture and functions like plugins to the database instances subscribing to the service while ensuring minimum interference for any other component.

4.1 Database Service Instances

In a Platform-as-a-service (PaaS) architecture deployed in the cloud, database service instances indicate the physical resources (like VM, containers, etc.) in which a database process, e.g., Postgresql, MySQL, MongoDB etc. runs [19, 20]. These database instances are provisioned and managed by the platform service provider, and the applications of the end user bind to these database processes for leveraging the data-persistence features. As showcased in Fig. 2, there could be multiple database instances, each having its own database process running within. The primary roles of a database service agent are to ensure the database process does not crash, ensure the high availability of a cluster, monitor the health of the cluster, etc. Additionally, if the database service instances choose to subscribe to the tuning service, the agent will read the metrics of the database process and send it over to the tuning service as per the configured frequency. The agent also communicates the current knob configuration of the database process to the tuning service. The agent places a request to the tuning service

Fig. 2: Proposed ADBaaS architecture

and then applies the recommendation (recommended knobs) received from the tuning service to the database process.

4.2 Data Management Module

The data-management module is the component solely responsible for any interaction between the tuning service and the database service instance. This module contains Data Federation Agent, which further consists of various types of adaptors for each database type. Adaptors are the components that facilitate communication of any generic module with various database types, agnostic of the specific nuances of the various database types. Since the tuning service is a generic component that can cater to various types of databases, hence this adapter becomes an essential component.

4.3 Tuning Service

The tuning service deployment is divided into two modules, primary tuner and secondary tuner. There has been a conscious rationale behind segregating the service deployment into two separate modules. One obvious reason is the segregation of concerns, separating the execution of on-demand tasks on one system and the execution of background tasks on another system. On-demand tasks will include operations like obtaining recommendations from the GPR module, whereas background tasks will include operations like retraining the models and aggregating experiences gathered from other global installations of the tuning service. Thus, both categories perform very cost-intensive operations. Isolating the two operations in separate resources having identically computing capacity seems justified and prevents unnecessary spikes in physical resource requirement.

Lastly, since operations like retraining can occur at any point and could reduce the performance of the tuning service, separating the process into another system ensures that the primary tuning service always performs at optimum levels, irrespective of the retraining tasks. The standard platform auto-scaler responsible for scaling the (primary and secondary) VM's based on load conditions.

- Primary Tuner This VM receives the on-demand recommendation requests, i.e., $\langle k_i, m_i \rangle W_n$, from a database. For each request, a task is created buffered in the job queue, and executed serially. Now in the first step, the workload mapping classifies the task to one of the most similar workloads seen and then uses the data of the mapped workload to train a GPR. Upon training, the GPR yields a set of optimal knob recommendations. The mapping workload engine always uses the current model in the cache for classification. This VM accesses all the workload data from the common SQL data store. This VM is also featured by Monitoring Agents and Platform Orchestrator Agents, which facilitate all the lifecycle operations and health monitoring.
- Secondary Tuner This VM is responsible for running background tasks such as factor analysis, clustering, and feature extraction. These tasks help in reducing data dimensions for increasing the overall efficacy of tasks triggered from Primary tuners. This VM also has a re-tuner module that performs the retraining of the proposed Neural Network and then transfers the learning to the primary tuner VM in JSON formats. This VM has a job scheduler, which periodically schedules the background tasks. The retraining module reads the flags from common data stores and initiates retraining. This VM is also featured by monitoring agents and platform Orchestrators.

4.4 Central Tuning Agent

Since the tuning service can be deployed in multiple landscapes and environments, it is expected that the service must be exposed to diverse learning experiences in multiple environments. The idea here is to leverage the learning gained by the tuning service in one landscape by all other deployments of the service. This is the primary role of the Central Tuning agent. The agent is globally connected to all the deployments of the tuning service in different environments. The global deployment could be restricted to a certain platform provider, and the discretion of learning can be decided by the platform service provider. The central tuning agent collects the learning models and data points of the tuning service across environments and stores this accumulated data in a central data repository. This new data is fed to the secondary tuner for updating the model with the new data points via a periodically triggered retraining module execution.

5 Overcoming Training Challenges

It is important to figure out the optimal timestamps when re-training the neural network. From production-based scenarios, the following reasons could be identified and attributed to why retraining is required.

- *Add of new database instances*: When a new database service instance, D_{n+1}^{new} subscribes to the tuning service, a new workload W_n^{new} is created in the tuner repository to store the experiences from D_{n+1}^{new} . Now as the total workloads stored have changed i.e., n to $n + 1$, the total number of classes for the ANN also changes.
- *Change of global ranked metrics and knobs*: When the background task in the secondary tuner-VM runs, it produces a new set of global ranked metrics and knobs. This causes a change in data dimensions. Empirically, the change in data dimensions also impacts the accuracy and error rate of the model.
- *Classification error rate increases*: Known data points are sent to the classifier periodically, upon which the accuracy rate and error rate are compared against thresholds. In this case, it is possible that retraining by considering the points in a buffer may increase the accuracy rate or reduce the error rate.
- *Evenly distribution of Softmax probabilities*: The Softmax activation function at the classification layer of the model returns probabilities for a data point that belong to a class. In many cases, it is observed that the probabilities are evenly distributed. One such example is, let’s consider, there are 3 classes, and the softmax probabilities are $\{0.323, 0.30, 0.314\}$. Here the class with a probability of 0.323 clearly wins the margin. However, the other classes also have a very near chance of winning. In such a situation again, it is assumed that retraining with all new possible points will make the probability distribution uneven and avoid certain scenarios.

The background of pruning/ranking tasks responsible for changing global ranked knobs and metrics run periodically. If the globally ranked knobs and metrics change with the trigger of background pruning/ranking, then at the same instance, retraining is also triggered. Apart from the dimension change issues, a common unified solution to other identified problems can be measured the probability distributions using entropy. Shannon entropy [21] of a discrete random variable X can be defined as:

$$H_n(X) = - \sum_{i=1}^n p(x_i) \log(p(x_i)) \quad (1)$$

where, $p(x_i)$ is the probability of i^{th} outcome of X . We define the similarity index as a measure of the probability distribution, which returns the number of elements (in % scale) having nearly similar probability. Fig. 3 depicts the variation of entropy based on a similarity index for a different set of classes. In

the production system, the threshold value for entropy is determined statically by fixing the number of classes and similarity index.

Fig. 3: Entropy variations

During classification, each time entropy value for the probabilities is calculated and then compared against the threshold. If the entropy value is greater than the threshold, the system retrains the model with the sole condition that at least one of the workloads (W_n) has one new point apart from the source workload. The incoming data point $\langle k_i, m_i \rangle \in W_n^{source}$, for which the entropy value has been violated, is statically mapped to the workload W_n^{target} , that has maximum mapping frequency for workload W_n^{source} . The maximum value of Shannon entropy for X , with a total n possible outcomes, is $\log(n)$. This happens when the probability of a data point in each class becomes equal. The value of $\eta(X)$ is ranging from 0 to 1, i.e., $\eta(X) \in [0, 1]$. This helps in determining the threshold value of entropy.

6 Performance Evaluation

The experiments were conducted on the AWS landscape, where the infrastructure resources were provisioned by Cloud Foundry [22] managed by Bosh [23]. The tuner deployment consists of 12 tuner instances - m4.xlarge with 4vCPU and 16GB memory, 5 config-director instances - m4.xlarge. A total of 80 live-database deployments (spawned through t2.small, t2.medium, m4.large, t2.large, and m4.xlarge VM types) to the tuning have been considered. For evaluating the experiments, PostgreSQL (v9.6) was used. All the tuner instances collected data from one common data repository, which is shared by all tuner instances. This instance also has an m4.xlarge configuration. The bare service replicas were created, one for each plan and were used to test the recommendations. We considered 10 minute observation time for YCSB and Wikipedia and 5 minutes observation time for TPCC. Table 1 shows F1 scores and accuracy obtained

Table 1: Performance summary

Production Data	Ottertune		Proposed Model	
	F1-Score	Accuracy	F1-Score	Accuracy
W=100 m=30	0.435	0.441	0.867	0.877
W=100 m=500	0.871	0.866	0.938	0.933
W=200 m=30	0.323	0.321	0.865	0.852
W=200 m=500	0.914	0.922	0.895	0.903
W=300 m=30	0.241	0.242	0.822	0.822
W=300 m=500	0.821	0.841	0.856	0.887

under different scenarios. Here W represents the number of workloads, and m is the data points per workload. For instance, in 100 workloads and 500 data points/ workload scenarios, the F1-score is 93.8% and accuracy is 93.3% which is $\approx 8.0\%$ improvement over Ottertune (State-of-the-art model).

Fig. 4: Retraining variations on production environment.

Fig. 4 shows the frequency of re-training requests triggered when the tuner deployment was hooked with a different set of production systems subjected to varying entropy values. Here, it is observed that with lower values of entropy, more re-training requests are getting triggered. This data can become extremely helpful for an admin to make decisions for optimal values of entropy (based on the similarity index) following the cost of each retraining w.r.t the provisioning cost perspective. Thus, depending on the performance trade-off, the admin can decide on the threshold. Fig. 5 showcases another scenario. Here, the tuner had already trained offline with a maximum of write-oriented workloads and significantly fewer read-oriented workloads (110 write workloads and 8 read-oriented workloads). Thus, the setup remains the same as the previous experiment. However, the source workload is highly randomized with a non-uniform mixture of read-write queries. OST engine, owing to its limitation of mapping the entire source workload to the target, tries to match all the data points in the source workload and, quite obviously, doesn't find any suitable target workload. Thus, owing to the other limitation of including the source workload as the target work-

Fig. 5: Average throughput for different data point sets in source workload

load, it maps to the source workload. Thus, the throughput always remains the same, which is average for all scenarios. The proposed work also suffers from the same limitation and performs poorly initially due to incorrect mapping. However, the retraining module is triggered to ensure proper training of the model. Thus, gradually the performance of the proposed work improves and can adjust to different scenarios.

Fig. 6 illustrates the general cold-start problem. Here, the tuner had already seen a maximum of write-oriented workloads and very few read-oriented workloads (110 write workloads and 8 read-oriented workloads). Here the workload is the execution of some preset load like read, write, or a combination of both, which helps the tuner learn and give appropriate knob configuration in real scenarios. In one case the source workload starts from no data points, where we observed reduced throughput initially for the OST approach, as shown in Fig. 6a. Due to the paucity of data, there are many wrong mappings. Hence non-optimal recommendations are generated. With the OST approach, due to incorrect mappings, the throughput of the database decreases, and later all the experiences in the source workload go with the cascading effect of sub-optimal experiences ending at self-mapping. However, with the proposed approach, we see better throughput as we minimize the cold start problem and restrict self-mapping. However, when the data points increase in the source workload, the accuracy of mapping increases, as shown in Fig. 6b. Hence, the GPR engine produces optimal recommendations causing an expected increase in throughput.

7 Concluding Remarks

This work presents a Neural Network based classification approach for optimally mapping the production workloads to the closest resembling target workloads. The challenges associated with the current OST's workload mapping approach are identified, and then a robust solution is proposed which can handle real-time production scenarios. While introducing a classification approach, an additional

(a) Bootstrapped with minimum 200 points per workload.

(b) Bootstrapped with minimum 700 points per workload.

Fig. 6: Average throughput for different data-point sets in source workload.

cost of retraining is encountered. The proposed approach is modified such that the cost of retraining is minimized from the perspective of provisioning and scalability challenges. Further, the solution is deployed on various cloud systems, and the performance is evaluated and compared with the prior solutions. A significant improvement in the accuracy of classification is achieved in the current approach. The solution is considered to be feasible for large-scale deployment of databases on a real-time system for keeping the database performance optimal at all times. Although the proposed work optimizes the performance of the classification engine, improving the scalability of the tuner to accommodate more database instances could be an interesting problem to tackle.

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